

IPBES VA Chapter 2 - Systematic review of value types in academic literature / IPBES values assessment (2.3)

Code: IPBES_VA_ 2.3

Versioning 01: (26.10.2020)

Versioning 02: (03.08.2021)

Versioning 03: (18.03.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4396289

Project leader(s):

Barbara Muraca (barbara.muraca@me.com)

Rachelle Gould (rgould@uvm.edu)

Researcher(s):

Dominic Lenzi (lenzi@mcc-berlin.net)

Christopher Raymond (christopher.raymond@helsinki.fi)

Austin Himes

Annalee Ring

Thomas Beery

Henrik Thoren

Sanna Ståhlhammar

Adam Hejnowicz

Data curator(s)

Mariana Cantú (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. The Scoping document for the values assessment established that chapter 2 must “assess the coverage of diverse conceptualizations of values with regard to nature and nature’s benefits to people. [...] The] values considered [...] will be intrinsic and instrumental

(including, e.g., use and non-use values, bequest values, option values and relational values).” The purpose of the review was to gather information on the types of values reported in the literature, in order to inform the full chapter, but particularly, sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.4. This literature review is part of stage 2 of the strategy used by chapter 2 for searching, reviewing and incorporating multiple sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection, with searches tailored to specific questions that permit to obtain a broader and deeper database to fulfil the mandate of the Scoping document.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review of literature found in three academic databases and Google Scholar until the date of the search (April 16, 2020).

Details of search 1: Web of science

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** April 16, 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 264 references (total resulting from the combination of all search results for each search string, and removing duplicates)
- **Search terms:**

TS=("relational value*" AND "nature's contribution* to people")

TS=("relational value*" AND "ecosystem service*")

TS=("instrumental value*" AND "nature's contribution* to people")

TS=("instrumental value*" AND "ecosystem service*")

TS=("intrinsic value*" AND "nature's contribution* to people")

TS=("intrinsic value*" AND "ecosystem service*")

TS=("relational value*" NEAR/3 "natur*")

TS=("intrinsic value*" NEAR/3 "natur*")

TS=("instrumental value*" NEAR/3 "natur*")

Details of search 2: EBSCOhost (Academic Search Premier)

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** EBSCOhost (Academic Search Premier)
- **Exact search date:** April 16, 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 91 references (total resulting from the combination of all search results for each search string, and removing duplicates)
- **Search terms:**

(TI "relational value*" OR SU "relational value*" OR AB "relational value*" OR KW "relational value*") AND (TI "ecosystem service*" OR SU "ecosystem service*" OR AB "ecosystem service*" OR KW "ecosystem service*")

(TI "relational value*" OR SU "relational value*" OR AB "relational value*" OR KW "relational value*") AND (TI "nature's contribution* to people" OR SU "nature's contribution* to people" OR AB "nature's contribution* to people" OR KW "nature's contribution* to people")

(TI "intrinsic value*" OR SU "intrinsic value*" OR AB "intrinsic value*" OR KW "intrinsic value*") AND (TI "ecosystem service*" OR SU "ecosystem service*" OR AB "ecosystem service*" OR KW "ecosystem service*")

(TI "intrinsic value*" OR SU "intrinsic value*" OR AB "intrinsic value*" OR KW "intrinsic value*") AND (TI "nature's contribution* to people" OR SU "nature's contribution* to people" OR AB "nature's contribution* to people" OR KW "nature's contribution* to people")

(TI "instrumental value*" OR SU "instrumental value*" OR AB "instrumental value*" OR KW "instrumental value*") AND (TI "ecosystem service*" OR SU "ecosystem service*" OR AB "ecosystem service*" OR KW "ecosystem service*")

(TI "instrumental value*" OR SU "instrumental value*" OR AB "instrumental value*" OR KW "instrumental value*") AND (TI "nature's contribution* to people" OR SU "nature's contribution* to people" OR AB "nature's contribution* to people" OR KW "nature's contribution* to people")

(TI "instrumental value*" OR SU "instrumental value*" OR AB "instrumental value*" OR KW "instrumental value*") AND (TI "nature's contribution* to people" OR SU "nature's contribution* to people" OR AB "nature's contribution* to people" OR KW "nature's contribution* to people")

(TI "intrinsic value*" OR SU "intrinsic value*" OR AB "intrinsic value*" OR KW "intrinsic value*") N3 (TI "natur*" OR SU "natur*" OR AB "natur*" OR KW "natur*")

(TI "instrumental value*" OR SU "instrumental value*" OR AB "instrumental value*" OR KW "instrumental value*") N3 (TI "natur*" OR SU "natur*" OR AB "natur*" OR KW "natur*")

(TI "relational value*" OR SU "relational value*" OR AB "relational value*" OR KW "relational value*") N3 (TI "natur*" OR SU "natur*" OR AB "natur*" OR KW "natur*")

Details of search 3: Scopus and Google Scholar

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Scopus, Google Scholar
- **Exact search date:** April 16, 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 328 references (total resulting from the combination of all search results for each search string, and removing duplicates)
- **Search terms:**

TITLE-ABS-KEY (("ecosystem service*" OR "nature's contribution* to people") AND ("relational value*" OR "instrumental value*" OR "intrinsic value*"))

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("relational value*" OR "instrumental value*" OR "intrinsic value*") W/3 ("natur*")

Screening criteria based on expert knowledge was applied to the raw references to select the relevant files to the review **(R1)**. This resulted in the 284 screened references found in file **(A)**.

- **Sample extracted (A):** 284
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Authors
 - Article Title
 - Year
 - Link or DOI
- **Location and format of the data:** IPBES_VA_2.3_05-2020_(A).csv
- **Treatment applied:** Title and abstract were analysed based on expert knowledge. This led to selecting relevant records for the review (284) **(R1)**.

Treatment applied: To begin with the coding process, PDFs in English, Spanish, Portuguese, Polish, Russian and German were retrieved. Only 260 PDFs out of the 284 records were accessed. From these 260 retrieved PDFs, 16 were in a language not available for the reviewers, and thus were not fully read and coded.

The 244 records in **(B)** were fully read and coded using 14 codes **(R2)**. Out of these, 5 were not considered relevant enough to be coded. In consequence, only 239 papers were coded.

- **Sample extracted:** 239
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - ID
 - Reviewer Name
 - Author
 - Article Title
 - Year
 - Link or DOI
 - PDF available
 - PDF language
 - Coded
- **Location and format of the data:** IPBES_VA_2.3_06-2020_(B).csv
- **Treatment applied:** 239 PDFs were fully read and coded according to **(R2)**.

A report of the qualitative and quantitative analyses, as well as summary of definitions and overlapping meanings of each specific value type, is presented in **(C)**. The analyses were based on the information resulting from coding 239 records found in **(B)**.

After analyses were completed, 32 new records were added with the purpose of complementing information. The decision on adding these records was based on expert knowledge. The list of the 32 added references can be found in **(D)**.

Sub-review of the data focused on framing

One of the codes in **(R2)** allowed reviewers to identify papers addressing the issue of framing in environmental values and valuation. A specific analysis of the information extracted through this code was performed.

Out of the 239 coded records in **(B)**, 115 records presented information on value types/ways of knowing being obscured and/or prioritised, and clarified this information in two subsequent codes: 'values obscured/prioritised' and 'clarify how values or knowledge are being obscured or prioritised'. These 115 records can be found in **(E)**.

- **Sample extracted (E):** 115
- **Fields extracted (E):**
 - ID
 - Reviewer name
 - Authors
 - Article Title

- Year
- Link or DOI
- Paper address some value types/ways of knowing being obscured and/or others prioritised
- **Location and format of the data:** IPBES_VA_2.3_07-2020_(E).csv
- **Treatment applied (R3):** information regarding “types/ways of knowing being obscured and/or prioritised” (as coded in **(R2)**), was summarised and analysed as described in **(R3)**.

For each of the records in **(E)**, the information extracted through the code ‘clarify how values or knowledge are being obscured or prioritised’ was summarised in 1-5 sentences. These summaries were analysed as described in **(R3)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.3_05-2020_(A)	csv	45 KB	Database with 284 records obtained through the screening of raw references.
B	IPBES_VA_2.3_06-2020_(B)	csv	519 KB	Database with 260 records for which PDF was available. 239 of these were coded.
C	IPBES_VA_2.3_07-2020_(C)	pdf	383 KB	Analysis report of the 239 records coded.
D	IPBES_VA_2.3_12-2020_(D)	pdf	129 KB	List of the 32 references added to complete the analysis.
E	IPBES_VA_2.3_07-2020_(E)	csv	55 KB	Database with 115 records which were coded under the code “value types/ways of knowing being obscured and/or prioritized”.
R2	IPBES_VA_2.3_06_2020_R2	pdf	263 KB	Codes and description of codification process used to analyse 239 records found in (B) .
R3	IPBES_VA_2.3_07-2020_R3	txt	2 KB	Description of the analysis applied to 115 records found in (E) .